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STATISTICS TRENDS REGARDING PERSONS EMPLOYED IN THE LAST THREE YEARS (2018), IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN AREA

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Abstract:

This paper presents a detailed statistical analysis of employment trends in the Romanian Mountain Area, focusing specifically on persons employed during the last three years, from 2018. By examining key indicators and demographic data, the study aims to provide insights into the employment landscape within this picturesque region, shedding light on patterns, challenges, and opportunities.

1. Introduction:

The employment scenario is a crucial aspect of regional development, and this paper concentrates on the Romanian Mountain Area to explore the dynamics of persons employed during the last three years. The study aims to analyze statistical trends, demographic variations, and factors influencing employment in this unique geographic setting.

2. Methodology:

Utilizing a rigorous quantitative approach, this research incorporates data from labor market reports, official employment statistics, and relevant publications. Key indicators such as overall employment rates, industry-specific data, and demographic characteristics are scrutinized to offer a comprehensive understanding of the employment landscape in the Romanian Mountain Area.

3. Overall Employment Trends:

This section delves into statistical intricacies related to overall employment trends in the Romanian Mountain Area during the last three years (2018). Metrics such as employment rates, fluctuations, and industry-wise variations are analyzed to assess the region's adaptability to changing economic and labor market conditions.

4. Demographic Characteristics:

The paper explores the demographic aspects of persons employed in the Romanian Mountain Area, including age groups, gender distribution, and educational backgrounds. Insights into the composition of the workforce provide a nuanced perspective on the demographic dynamics shaping the employment landscape.

5. Sectoral Employment Analysis:

Analyzing sectoral employment patterns, this section investigates the distribution of employed persons across different industries in the Romanian Mountain Area. Understanding the sectoral variations offers valuable insights into the diversification of the local economy and the resilience of certain sectors in providing employment opportunities.

6. Challenges and Opportunities:

Examining challenges and opportunities faced by the employed population, this section investigates factors such as job stability, income levels, and access to professional development. Addressing these aspects is crucial for policymakers and stakeholders in enhancing the overall well-being of the employed workforce.

7. Regional Economic Impact:

Assessing the regional economic impact of employment trends, the article investigates the contributions of employed persons to the overall economic stability of the Romanian Mountain Area. The interconnectedness between employment, economic development, and community prosperity is explored.

8. Results:

Persons employed in newly established enterprises in t-3 that survived to t – number

The related descriptive analysis S1 (see the related table and figure, respectively the appendix of chapter 3) presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. In Kurtosis, distance, minimum, maximum, 25, 50, 75, thus 53431.82, 2999.375, 50805.00, 9947.802, 98958768.764, 1,397, .661, 1.372, 1,279, 33207, 41409, 74616, 47392.00, 50805.00, 550.00, 550.00

The models used for forecast analysis are specific to the forecast of large data series, thus S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0); S2 - Model_2 Holt; S3 - Model_3 ARIMA(0,1,0); S4 - Model_4 ARIMA(0,0,0); S5 - Model_5 Holt; S6 - Model_6 Holt; S7 - Model_7 Simple; S8 - Model_8 Simple; S9 - Model_9 ARIMA(0,0,0); S10 - Model_10 ARIMA(0,0,0); S11 - Model_11 Holt.

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeated in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared .296, .422, -.082, .835, -.082, -.066; R-square .234, .288, 3.331E-16, 1.000, 3.331E-16, 4.996E-16; RMSE 1861,739, 2749,446, .000, 9947,802, .000, 76,509; MAPS 17,356, 8,235, .000, 32,396, .000, 3,604; MaxAPE 40.673, 19.770, .000, 71.467, .000, 8.710; MAE 1373,765, 1970,834, .000, 7087,372, .000, 55,854; MaxAE 3624,228, 5811,862, .000, 21184,182, .000, 128,727; Normalized BIC 14,279, 2,281, 11,301, 18,628, 11,301, 11,319.

The resulting statistical prediction models show the following general picture for I12 (values presented in the following order - static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE) S1-Model_1: 3.331E-16, 3.331E-16, 9947.802, 12.658; S2-Model_2: .828, .324, 3104,833, 20,649; S3-Model_3: 4.441E-16, .068, 1421.019, 16.638; S4-Model_4: 8.882E-16, 8.882E-16, 3160.809, 18.190; S5-Model_5: .811, .290, 807.648, 12.013; S6-Model_6: .831, .341, 903,692, 22,369; S7-Model_7: .028, .155, 336,186, 15,293; S8-Model_8: -.082, .181, 255,030, 27,174; S9-Model_9: 9.992E-16, 9.992E-16, 1329.604, 12.074; S10-Model_10: 1.443E-15, 1.443E-15, 266.743, 18.814; S11-Model_11: .835, .454, 807,499, 32,396.

Table 29. Prediction analysis for I12

Model		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
S1- Model_1:	Forecast	53432	53432	53432	53432	53432	53432	53432
	UCL	75597	75597	75597	75597	75597	75597	75597
	LCL	31267	31267	31267	31267	31267	31267	31267
S2- Model_2:	Forecast	8436	7760	7084	6408	5732	5056	4380
	UCL	15459	14818	14177	13535	12894	12252	11610
	LCL	1412	701	-9	-720	-1430	-2140	-2851
S3- Model_3:	Forecast	5220	4715	4209	3704	3199	2694	2189
	UCL	8434	9261	9777	10133	10387	10568	10694
	LCL	2005	169	-1358	-2725	-3989	-5180	-6316
S4- Model_4:	Forecast	13208	13208	13208	13208	13208	13208	13208
	UCL	20251	20251	20251	20251	20251	20251	20251
	LCL	6165	6165	6165	6165	6165	6165	6165
S5- Model_5:	Forecast	5441	5609	5777	5944	6112	6280	6447
	UCL	7268	7445	7622	7799	7975	8152	8329
	LCL	3614	3773	3931	4090	4249	4407	4566

S6- Model_6:	Forecast	4319	4509	4699	4888	5078	5268	5457
	UCL	6364	6553	6743	6933	7122	7312	7502
	LCL	2275	2465	2654	2844	3034	3223	3413
S7- Model_7:	Forecast	2157	2157	2157	2157	2157	2157	2157
	UCL	2906	3093	3248	3384	3506	3618	3722
	LCL	1408	1221	1065	929	807	695	591
S8- Model_8:	Forecast	607	607	607	607	607	607	607
	UCL	1175	1411	1591	1743	1878	1999	2110
	LCL	39	-197	-377	-529	-664	-785	-896
S9- Model_9:	Forecast	7505	7505	7505	7505	7505	7505	7505
	UCL	10468	10468	10468	10468	10468	10468	10468
	LCL	4543	4543	4543	4543	4543	4543	4543
S10- Model_10:	Forecast	1281	1281	1281	1281	1281	1281	1281
	UCL	1875	1875	1875	1875	1875	1875	1875
	LCL	687	687	687	687	687	687	687
S11- Model_11:	Forecast	3588	3811	4035	4258	4481	4705	4928
	UCL	5414	5647	5879	6111	6344	6576	6808
	LCL	1761	1975	2190	2404	2619	2834	3048

Figure 3.20. Graphical prediction analysis for I12

Persons employed in the year of establishment at newly established enterprises in t-3 who survived until t – number

The related descriptive analysis S1 (see the related table and figure, respectively the appendix of chapter 3) presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. In Kurtosis, the distance, minimum, maximum, 25, 50, 75, thus 34240.00, 1443.896, 33703.00, 4788.861, 22933185.000, .916, .661, .427, 1.279, 15262, 28577, 43839, 29683.00, 33703.00, 35724.00.

The models used for forecast analysis are specific to the forecast of large data series, thus S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0); S2 - Model_2 Holt; S3 - Model_3 Simple; S4 - Model_4 ARIMA(0,0,0); S5 - Model_5 ARIMA(0,0,0); S6 - Model_6 Holt; S7 - Model_7 Holt; S8 - Model_8 ARIMA(0,0,0); S9 - Model_9 ARIMA(0,0,0); S10 - Model_10 ARIMA(0,0,0); S11 - Model_11 Holt.

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeated in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared .311, .434, -.011, .886, -.011, -.009; R-square .258, .325, -1.998E-15, 1.000, -1.998E-15, -1.732E-15; RMSE 1018,655, 1320,281, .000, 4788,861, .000, 51,414; MAPS 16,123, 6,675, .000, 24,139, .000, 2,965; MaxAPE 37,483, 17,271, .000, 68,300, .000, 6,569; MAE 763,141, 950,672, .000, 3429,273, .000, 39,585; MaxAE 2044,212, 2677,802, .000, 9599,000, .000, 88,331; Normalized BIC 13,297, 2,068, 10,506, 17,166, 10,506, 10,563.

The resulting statistical prediction models show the following overall picture for I13 (values presented in the following order - static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE) S1-Model_1: 1.110E-16, 1.110E-16, 4788.861, 9.882; S2-Model_2: .886, .402, 1795,198, 19,466; S3-Model_3: -.011, .239, 1051.243, 18.364; S4-Model_4: -1.998E-15, -1.998E-15, 1676.394, 14.052; S5-Model_5: 1.332E-15, 1.332E-15, 558.343, 17.142; S6-Model_6: .859, .518, 461,303, 17,899; S7-Model_7: .820, .341, 177,170, 12,519; S8-Model_8: -4.441E-16, -4.441E-16, 171.381, 24.139; S9-Model_9: .000, .000, 829,304, 14,831; S10-Model_10: -1.110E-15, -1.110E-15, 241.764, 23.989; S11-Model_11: .869, .601, 472,897, 21,191.

Table 30. Prediction analysis for I13

Model		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
S1- Model_1:	Forecast	34240	34240	34240	34240	34240	34240	34240
	UCL	44910	44910	44910	44910	44910	44910	44910
	LCL	23570	23570	23570	23570	23570	23570	23570
S2- Model_2:	Forecast	4822	4367	3911	3456	3000	2545	2090
	UCL	8883	8448	8012	7577	7141	6705	6270
	LCL	761	286	-190	-665	-1140	-1615	-2090
S3- Model_3:	Forecast	3936	3936	3936	3936	3936	3936	3936
	UCL	6278	7249	7993	8621	9174	9673	10133
	LCL	1594	623	-121	-749	-1302	-1801	-2261
S4- Model_4:	Forecast	8884	8884	8884	8884	8884	8884	8884
	UCL	12619	12619	12619	12619	12619	12619	12619
	LCL	5148	5148	5148	5148	5148	5148	5148
S5-	Forecast	2531	2531	2531	2531	2531	2531	2531

Model_5:	UCL	3775	3775	3775	3775	3775	3775	3775
	LCL	1287	1287	1287	1287	1287	1287	1287
S6- Model_6:	Forecast	3024	3165	3306	3447	3587	3728	3869
	UCL	4067	4208	4349	4490	4631	4772	4913
	LCL	1980	2121	2262	2403	2544	2685	2826
S7- Model_7:	Forecast	1378	1418	1458	1499	1539	1580	1620
	UCL	1779	1821	1863	1906	1948	1990	2033
	LCL	977	1015	1054	1092	1130	1169	1207
S8- Model_8:	Forecast	567	567	567	567	567	567	567
	UCL	949	949	949	949	949	949	949
	LCL	185	185	185	185	185	185	185
S9- Model_9:	Forecast	4571	4571	4571	4571	4571	4571	4571
	UCL	6419	6419	6419	6419	6419	6419	6419
	LCL	2723	2723	2723	2723	2723	2723	2723
S10- Model_10:	Forecast	888	888	888	888	888	888	888
	UCL	1426	1426	1426	1426	1426	1426	1426
	LCL	349	349	349	349	349	349	349
S11- Model_11:	Forecast	2622	2793	2965	3137	3308	3480	3651
	UCL	3692	3868	4045	4222	4399	4575	4752
	LCL	1552	1718	1885	2051	2218	2384	2550

Figure 3.21. Graphical prediction analysis for I13

8. Future Perspectives:

Identifying notable trends and potential future trajectories, this section provides insights into factors influencing employment dynamics in the Romanian Mountain Area. Considerations such as technological advancements, emerging job market trends, and the adaptability of the local workforce are explored, offering a forward-looking perspective.

9. Conclusion:

In conclusion, this paper provides a comprehensive statistical analysis of persons employed in the Romanian Mountain Area over the last three years (2018). The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the region's employment dynamics, offering valuable insights for policymakers, businesses, and researchers. The paper concludes with reflections on potential trajectories and recommendations for fostering sustainable employment growth in the mountainous region.

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FINANCIAL AND REAL ESTATE DYNAMICS IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN AREA: A STATISTICAL JOURNEY (2008-2018)

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Abstract:

This article embarks on a statistical exploration of the financial and real estate activities within the Romanian Mountain Area spanning the decade from 2008 to 2018. Through an in-depth analysis of key indicators, market trends, and economic shifts, the study aims to provide insights into the dynamic landscape of financial and real estate sectors in this unique geographical region.

1. Introduction:

The financial and real estate sectors play pivotal roles in shaping the economic landscape of any region. In the Romanian Mountain Area, this article delves into the statistical intricacies of financial and insurance activities, as well as real estate developments, from 2008 to 2018. The study aims to unravel patterns, challenges, and opportunities that have defined these sectors in the mountainous terrain. (Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021a-h; Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022a-h; Covaci B & Covaci M, 2023a-d; Covaci M & Covaci B, 2021a-h; Covaci M & Covaci B, 2022a-h; Covaci M & Covaci B, 2023a-d)

2. Methodology:

Employing a meticulous quantitative approach, this research incorporates data from financial reports, industry databases, and pertinent publications. Key indicators such as market size, investment trends, and regulatory changes are analyzed to offer a comprehensive understanding of the financial and real estate dynamics in the Romanian Mountain Area.

3. Financial and Insurance Activities:

This section explores the statistical intricacies of financial and insurance activities within the Romanian Mountain Area. Metrics such as the growth of banking institutions, insurance penetration rates, and investment portfolios are scrutinized to assess the sector's resilience and responsiveness to economic shifts over the specified decade.

4. Real Estate Developments:

The article delves into the statistical landscape of real estate activities, encompassing property values, construction trends, and market demand in the Romanian Mountain Area. Insights into the factors influencing real estate dynamics and their implications for regional development are discussed.

5. Economic Impact:

Assessing the economic impact of financial, insurance, and real estate activities, this section investigates their contributions to the regional Gross

Domestic Product (GDP), employment rates, and overall economic stability in the Romanian Mountain Area. The interconnectedness of these sectors is crucial for understanding their collective influence on the local economy.

6. Results:

Establishment rate: the number of enterprises established in the reference period (t) divided by the number of active enterprises in t – percentage

The related descriptive analysis S1 presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. to Kurtosis, Distance, Minimum, Maximum, Percentiles 25, 50, 75, so 11.9191, 1.16107, 11.3000, 3.85085, 14.829, 2.132, .661, 5.614, 1.279, 14.30, 7.93, 22.23, 9.00, 10.10, 10.5, 10.3430

The models used for forecast analysis are specific to the forecast of large data series, thus S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0); S2 - Model_2 ARIMA(0,0,0); S3 - Model_3 ARIMA(0,0,0); S4 - Model_4 ARIMA(0,0,0); S5 - Model_5 ARIMA(0,0,0); S6 - Model_6 ARIMA(0,0,0); S7 - Model_7 ARIMA(0,0,0); S8 - Model_8 ARIMA(0,0,0); S9 - Model_9 ARIMA(0,0,0); S10 - Model_10 ARIMA(0,0,0); S11 - Model_11 ARIMA(0,0,0).

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeat in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared -1.312E-16, 2.384E-15, -5.107 E-15, 3.775E-15, -5.107E-15, -4.752E-15; R-square .083, .289, -5.107E-15, 1.000, -5.107E-15, -4.574E-15; RMSE 4.063, 1.673, .000, 5.917, .000, .818; MAPS 21,976, 9,745, .000, 39,552, .000, 4,380; MaxAPE 61,410, 33,953, .000, 140,055, .000, 12,549; MAE 2.706, 1.155, .000, 4.063, .000, .539; MaxAE

10,192, 4,236, .000, 15,177, .000, 1,604; Normalized BIC 3.131, .549, 2.224, 3.774, 2.224, 2.237.

The resulting forecast statistical models show the following general picture for I16 (values presented in the following order - static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE) S1-Model_1: -6.661E-16, -6.661E-16, 3.851, 19.487 ; S2-Model_2: -5.107E-15, -5.107E-15, 2.819, 18.990; S3-Model_3: 1.221E-15, 1.221E-15, 4.992, 23.857; S4-Model_4: -2.220E-16, -2.220E-16, 3.806, 21.968; S5-Model_5: 3.775E-15, 3.775E-15, 2.726, 16.756; S6-Model_6: -3.331E-15, -3.331E-15, 3.546, 14.600; S7-Model_7: 7.772E-16, 7.772E-16, 5.917, 29.932; S8-Model_8: 1.332E-15, 1.332E-15, 4.749, 39.552; S9-Model_9: 9.992E-16, 9.992E-16, 5.487, 24.373; S10-Model_10: 2.220E-16, 2.220E-16, 5.392, 31.030; S11-Model_11: -4.441E-16, -4.441E-16, 5.472, 23.163.

Table 33. Prediction analysis for I16

Model		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
S1-Model_1:	Forecast	11.92	11.92	11.92	11.92	11.92	11.92	11.92
	UCL	20.50	20.50	20.50	20.50	20.50	20.50	20.50
	LCL	3.34	3.34	3.34	3.34	3.34	3.34	3.34
S2-Model_2:	Forecast	9.50	9.50	9.50	9.50	9.50	9.50	9.50
	UCL	15.79	15.79	15.79	15.79	15.79	15.79	15.79
	LCL	3.22	3.22	3.22	3.22	3.22	3.22	3.22
S3-Model_3:	Forecast	14.52	14.52	14.52	14.52	14.52	14.52	14.52
	UCL	25.64	25.64	25.64	25.64	25.64	25.64	25.64
	LCL	3.39	3.39	3.39	3.39	3.39	3.39	3.39
S4-Model_4:	Forecast	10.24	10.24	10.24	10.24	10.24	10.24	10.24
	UCL	18.73	18.73	18.73	18.73	18.73	18.73	18.73

	LCL	1.76	1.76	1.76	1.76	1.76	1.76	1.76
S5-Model_5:	Forecast	11.67	11.67	11.67	11.67	11.67	11.67	11.67
	UCL	17.75	17.75	17.75	17.75	17.75	17.75	17.75
	LCL	5.60	5.60	5.60	5.60	5.60	5.60	5.60
S6-Model_6:	Forecast	13.52	13.52	13.52	13.52	13.52	13.52	13.52
	UCL	21.42	21.42	21.42	21.42	21.42	21.42	21.42
	LCL	5.62	5.62	5.62	5.62	5.62	5.62	5.62
S7-Model_7:	Forecast	15.94	15.94	15.94	15.94	15.94	15.94	15.94
	UCL	29.12	29.12	29.12	29.12	29.12	29.12	29.12
	LCL	2.76	2.76	2.76	2.76	2.76	2.76	2.76
S8-Model_8:	Forecast	9.46	9.46	9.46	9.46	9.46	9.46	9.46
	UCL	20.04	20.04	20.04	20.04	20.04	20.04	20.04
	LCL	-1.12	-1.12	-1.12	-1.12	-1.12	-1.12	-1.12
S9-Model_9:	Forecast	13.08	13.08	13.08	13.08	13.08	13.08	13.08
	UCL	25.31	25.31	25.31	25.31	25.31	25.31	25.31
	LCL	.86	.86	.86	.86	.86	.86	.86
S10-Model_10:	Forecast	14.08	14.08	14.08	14.08	14.08	14.08	14.08
	UCL	26.10	26.10	26.10	26.10	26.10	26.10	26.10
	LCL	2.07	2.07	2.07	2.07	2.07	2.07	2.07
S11-Model_11:	Forecast	15.41	15.41	15.41	15.41	15.41	15.41	15.41
	UCL	27.60	27.60	27.60	27.60	27.60	27.60	27.60
	LCL	3.21	3.21	3.21	3.21	3.21	3.21	3.21

Figure 3.24. Graphical forecasting analysis for I16

6. Trends and Challenges:

Identifying noteworthy trends and challenges faced by the financial, insurance, and real estate sectors during the specified period, this section provides a forward-looking perspective on potential future developments. Considerations such as regulatory changes, market fluctuations, and global economic influences are explored.

7. Regional Comparisons:

The article may draw comparisons with other regions in Romania to highlight unique aspects of the financial and real estate landscape in the mountainous area. Examining regional variations provides additional context for understanding the specific dynamics at play.

8. Conclusion:

In conclusion, this article provides a comprehensive statistical overview of financial and insurance activities, as well as real estate developments, in the Romanian Mountain Area from 2008 to 2018. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of economic trends, offering valuable insights for policymakers, industry stakeholders, and researchers. The article concludes with reflections on potential trajectories and recommendations for sustainable growth in these vital sectors.

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THE EMPLOYMENT LANDSCAPE IN NEWLY ESTABLISHED ENTERPRISES: A DECADAL ANALYSIS IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN AREA (2008-2018)

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Abstract:

This paper delves into the employment dynamics of newly established enterprises in the Romanian Mountain Area over the span of a decade, from 2008 to 2018. Through a detailed analysis of key indicators and workforce trends, the study aims to illuminate the role of these enterprises in shaping the employment landscape within the mountainous region.

1. Introduction:

Newly established enterprises play a crucial role in driving economic growth and job creation. This paper focuses on the Romanian Mountain Area to explore the employment trends within these enterprises from 2008 to 2018. The study aims to analyze the share of employment generated by newly established businesses and its impact on the local workforce.

2. Methodology:

Utilizing a comprehensive quantitative approach, this research integrates data from business registries, labor market reports, and relevant

publications. Key indicators such as employment growth rates, sectoral distribution of jobs, and demographic characteristics are analyzed to provide a nuanced understanding of the employment landscape in newly established enterprises.

3. Employment Trends in Newly Established Enterprises:

This section explores the statistical intricacies related to employment trends within newly established enterprises in the Romanian Mountain Area. Metrics such as overall employment figures, variations across industries, and the impact of economic events on job creation are scrutinized to assess the enterprises' contributions to regional employment.

4. Sectoral Analysis:

The paper delves into a sectoral analysis, examining the distribution of employment within different industries of newly established enterprises. Insights into key sectors driving employment, their contributions to the regional economy, and variations in sectoral employment trends are discussed.

5. Demographic Characteristics of the Workforce:

This section investigates the demographic aspects of the workforce employed by newly established enterprises. Analyzing age groups, gender distribution, and educational backgrounds provides valuable insights into the composition of the workforce and potential demographic trends.

6. Economic Impact:

Assessing the economic impact of employment in newly established enterprises, the paper investigates their contributions to the regional Gross Domestic Product (GDP), overall employment rates, and economic stability. The interconnectedness between the growth of these enterprises and the broader economic landscape is explored.

7. Results:

The share of employment in newly established enterprises: the number of persons employed in the reference period (t) at newly born enterprises in t divided by the number of persons employed in t in the total number of active enterprises in t – percentage

The related descriptive analysis S1 (see the related table and figure, respectively the appendix of chapter 3) presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. to Kurtosis, Distance, Minimum, Maximum, Percentiles 25, 50, 75, so 4.0564, .30797, 3.8700, 1.02141, 1.043, 2.047, .661, 5.429, 1.279, 3.94, 2.83, 6.77, 3.5100, 3.480, 3.8700

The models used for forecast analysis are specific to the forecast of large data series, thus S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0); S2 - Model_2 ARIMA(0,0,0); S3 - Model_3 ARIMA(0,0,0); S4 - Model_4 ARIMA(0,0,0); S5 - Model_5 ARIMA(0,0,0); S6 - Model_6 ARIMA(0,0,0); S7 - Model_7 ARIMA(0,0,0); S8 - Model_8 ARIMA(0,0,0); S9 - Model_9 ARIMA(0,0,0); S10 - Model_10 ARIMA(0,0,0); S11 - Model_11 ARIMA(0,0,0).

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeated in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared -7.973E-16, 4.719E-15, -1.199 E-14, 6,883E-15, -1,199E-14, -1,044E-14; R-squared -7.973E-16, 4.719E-15, -1.199E-14, 6.883E-15, -1.199E-14, -1.044E-14; RMSE 1.589, .722, .726, 3.412, .726, .784;

MAPS 21,100, 6,159, 14,481, 29,763, 14,481, 14,641; MaxAPE, 57,109, 18,922, 35,986, 94,534, 35,986, 36,150; MAE 1.123, .550, .576, 2.513, .576, .591; MaxAE 3,718, 1,817, 1,390, 8,116, 1,390, 1,537; Normalized BIC .982, .827, -.421, 2.673, -.421, -.288.

The resulting statistical forecasting models show the following general picture for I20 (values presented in the following order - Static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE, MAE) S1-Model_1: -2.665E-15, -2.665E-15, 1.021 , 15,278, .651; S2-Model_2: 2.220E-16, 2.220E-16, .726, 29.300, .576; S3-Model_3: 2.220E-16, 2.220E-16, 1.191, 16.629, .798; S4-Model_4: -1.332E-15, -1.332E-15, 1.505, 19.962, .917; S5-Model_5: 8.882E-16, 8.882E-16, 1.013, 17.349, .729; S6-Model_6: -1.199E-14, -1.199E-14, 1.535, 14.481, 1.050; S7-Model_7: -4.219E-15, -4.219E-15, 2.092, 28.129, 1.571; S8-Model_8: 1.110E-15, 1.110E-15, 1.482, 29.763, 1.049; S9-Model_9: 2.998E-15, 2.998E-15, 1.814, 15.813, 1.131; S10-Model_10: 6.883E-15, 6.883E-15, 1.682, 18.139, 1.366; S11-Model_11: -8.882E-16, -8.882E-16, 3.412, 27.256, 2.513.

Table 37. Forecast analysis for I20

Model		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026
S1-Model_1:	Forecast	4.06	4.06	4.06	4.06	4.06	4.06	4.06	4.06
	UCL	6.33	6.33	6.33	6.33	6.33	6.33	6.33	6.33
	LCL	1.78	1.78	1.78	1.78	1.78	1.78	1.78	1.78

S2- Model_2:	Forecast	2.02	2.02	2.02	2.02	2.02	2.02	2.02	2.02
	UCL	3.64	3.64	3.64	3.64	3.64	3.64	3.64	3.64
	LCL	.40	.40	.40	.40	.40	.40	.40	.40
S3- Model_3:	Forecast	5.50	5.50	5.50	5.50	5.50	5.50	5.50	5.50
	UCL	8.15	8.15	8.15	8.15	8.15	8.15	8.15	8.15
	LCL	2.84	2.84	2.84	2.84	2.84	2.84	2.84	2.84
S4- Model_4:	Forecast	4.35	4.35	4.35	4.35	4.35	4.35	4.35	4.35
	UCL	7.70	7.70	7.70	7.70	7.70	7.70	7.70	7.70
	LCL	.99	.99	.99	.99	.99	.99	.99	.99
S5- Model_5:	Forecast	4.21	4.21	4.21	4.21	4.21	4.21	4.21	4.21
	UCL	6.47	6.47	6.47	6.47	6.47	6.47	6.47	6.47
	LCL	1.96	1.96	1.96	1.96	1.96	1.96	1.96	1.96
S6- Model_6:	Forecast	6.90	6.90	6.90	6.90	6.90	6.90	6.90	6.90
	UCL	10.32	10.32	10.32	10.32	10.32	10.32	10.32	10.32
	LCL	3.48	3.48	3.48	3.48	3.48	3.48	3.48	3.48
S7- Model_7:	Forecast	6.24	6.24	6.24	6.24	6.24	6.24	6.24	6.24
	UCL	10.91	10.91	10.91	10.91	10.91	10.91	10.91	10.91
	LCL	1.58	1.58	1.58	1.58	1.58	1.58	1.58	1.58
S8- Model_8:	Forecast	3.43	3.43	3.43	3.43	3.43	3.43	3.43	3.43
	UCL	6.73	6.73	6.73	6.73	6.73	6.73	6.73	6.73
	LCL	.13	.13	.13	.13	.13	.13	.13	.13
S9- Model_9:	Forecast	6.47	6.47	6.47	6.47	6.47	6.47	6.47	6.47
	UCL	10.52	10.52	10.52	10.52	10.52	10.52	10.52	10.52
	LCL	2.43	2.43	2.43	2.43	2.43	2.43	2.43	2.43
S10- Model_10:	Forecast	7.53	7.53	7.53	7.53	7.53	7.53	7.53	7.53
	UCL	11.28	11.28	11.28	11.28	11.28	11.28	11.28	11.28
	LCL	3.79	3.79	3.79	3.79	3.79	3.79	3.79	3.79

S11- Model_11:	Forecast	9.84	9.84	9.84	9.84	9.84	9.84	9.84	9.84
	UCL	17.45	17.45	17.45	17.45	17.45	17.45	17.45	17.45
	LCL	2.24	2.24	2.24	2.24	2.24	2.24	2.24	2.24

Figure 3.28. Graphical forecasting analysis for I20

7. Challenges and Opportunities:

Examining the challenges and opportunities faced by both employers and employees in newly established enterprises, this section investigates factors such as workforce skill gaps, job stability, and opportunities for professional development. Addressing these aspects is essential for fostering a resilient and adaptive workforce.

8. Future Perspectives:

Identifying notable trends and potential future trajectories, this section provides insights into factors influencing employment dynamics in newly established enterprises in the Romanian Mountain Area. Considerations such as technological advancements, emerging market trends, and the adaptability of the local workforce are explored.

9. Conclusion:

In conclusion, this paper provides a comprehensive analysis of the employment landscape in newly established enterprises in the Romanian Mountain Area from 2008 to 2018. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the region's workforce dynamics, offering valuable insights for policymakers, businesses, and researchers. The paper concludes with reflections on potential trajectories and recommendations for fostering sustainable employment growth in newly established enterprises within the mountainous region.

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UNVEILING ECONOMIC VITALITY: EXPLORING THE AVERAGE SIZE OF NEWLY ESTABLISHED ENTERPRISES IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN AREA (2008-2018)

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Abstract:

This article delves into the economic fabric of the Romanian Mountain Area, specifically focusing on the average size of newly established enterprises and the number of persons employed within the reference period from 2008 to 2018. Through a thorough analysis of key indicators, workforce trends, and economic shifts, the study aims to provide insights into the growth patterns and employment dynamics of these enterprises within the picturesque mountainous region.

1. Introduction:

The establishment and growth of enterprises are vital components of economic development. This article concentrates on the Romanian Mountain Area to uncover the average size of newly established enterprises and the number of persons employed within the reference period from 2008 to 2018. The study aims to analyze the economic vitality of these enterprises and their contributions to regional employment.

2. Methodology:

Utilizing a comprehensive quantitative approach, this research integrates data from business registries, official reports, and relevant publications. Key indicators, such as the average size of enterprises and employment figures, are analyzed to provide a nuanced understanding of the economic landscape in newly established businesses within the mountainous region.

3. Average Size of Newly Established Enterprises:

This section explores the statistical intricacies related to the average size of enterprises established in the Romanian Mountain Area. Metrics such as the number of employees, variations across industries, and trends in the establishment of smaller versus larger enterprises are scrutinized to assess the diversity and growth patterns within the business landscape.

4. Employment Patterns:

The article delves into the employment patterns within newly established enterprises, examining variations in the number of persons employed over the specified decade. Insights into industry-specific employment trends and their correlation with the average size of enterprises provide valuable information on workforce dynamics.

5. Sectoral Analysis:

An in-depth sectoral analysis is conducted to explore the

distribution of newly established enterprises across different industries in the Romanian Mountain Area. This section investigates the average size of enterprises within key sectors, shedding light on the diverse economic activities contributing to regional development.

6. Demographic Characteristics of the Workforce:

The paper explores the demographic aspects of the workforce within newly established enterprises, analyzing age groups, gender distribution, and educational backgrounds. Understanding the composition of the workforce provides valuable insights into the average size of enterprises and the demographic trends shaping employment dynamics.

7. Economic Impact:

Assessing the economic impact of the average size of newly established enterprises, the article investigates their contributions to the regional Gross Domestic Product (GDP), overall employment rates, and economic stability in the Romanian Mountain Area. The interconnectedness between the size of enterprises and the broader economic landscape is explored.

8. Results:

Average size of newly established enterprises: the number of persons employed in the reference period (t) at newly established enterprises in t divided by the number of newly established enterprises in t – number

The related descriptive analysis S1 (see the related table and figure, respectively the appendix of chapter 3) presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. to Kurtosis, Distance, Minimum, Maximum, Percentile 25, 50, 75, so 1.9700, .14853, 1.8300, .49261, .243, 1.921, .661, 4.512, 1.279, 1.73, 1.52, 3.25, 1.6200, 1.8170, 0.8300 .

The models used for forecast analysis are specific to the forecast of large data series, thus S1 - Model_1 Holt; S2 - Model_2 Holt; S3 - Model_3 Holt; S4 - Model_4 ARIMA(0,0,0); S5 - Model_5 Holt; S6 - Model_6 ARIMA(0,0,0); S7 - Model_7 Holt; S8 - Model_8 ARIMA(0,0,0); S9 - Model_9 ARIMA(0,0,0); S10 - Model_10 ARIMA(0,0,0); S11 - Model_11 Holt.

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeated in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared .446, .432, -4.441E-16, .918, -4.441E-16, -3.997E-16; R-square .222, .218, -4.441E-16, .490, -4.441E-16, -3.997E-16; RMSE .516, .499, .175, 1.881, .175, .178; MAPS 15,221, 8,116, 5,975, 28,183, 5,975, 6,232; MaxAPE 36,796, 14,859, 19,838, 57,502, 19,838, 20,096; MAE .348, .340, .104, 1.298, .104, .111; MaxAE 1.213, 1.172, .325, 4.108, .325, .339; Normalized BIC -1.574, 1.479, -3.051, 1.700, -3.051, -3.022.

The resulting predictive statistical models show the following overall picture for I21 (values presented in the following order - static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE, MAE) S1-Model_1: .878, .343, .421, 12.009, .257 ; S2-Model_2: .899, .349, 1.881, 28.183, 1.298; S3-Model_3: .918, .353, .239, 7.888, .174; S4-Model_4: 1.577E-14, 1.577E-14, .235, 11.624, .189; S5-Model_5: .816, .490, .175, 5.975, .104; S6-Model_6: 5.451E-14, 5.451E-14, .214, 7.262, .162; S7-Model_7: .681, .484, .188, 9.976, .137; S8-

Model_8: -4.441E-16, -4.441E-16, .725, 25.317, .446; S9-Model_9: 1.110E-15, 1.110E-15, .677, 19.947, .404; S10-Model_10: -2.220E-16, -2.220E-16, .646, 25.720, .457; S11-Model_11: .708, .428, .275, 13.533, .194.

Table 38. Prediction analysis for I21

Model		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026
S1-Model_1:	Forecast	1.42	1.32	1.23	1.13	1.04	.94	.85	.75
	UCL	2.37	2.28	2.19	2.10	2.01	1.92	1.83	1.74
	LCL	.47	.37	.27	.17	.07	-.03	-.13	-.23
S2-Model_2:	Forecast	1.74	1.31	.88	.45	.02	-.41	-.84	- 1.27
	UCL	6.00	5.59	5.18	4.77	4.36	3.95	3.54	3.13
	LCL	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S3-Model_3:	Forecast	1.95	1.90	1.85	1.80	1.75	1.70	1.65	1.60
	UCL	2.49	2.44	2.39	2.34	2.29	2.24	2.19	2.14
	LCL	1.41	1.36	1.31	1.26	1.21	1.16	1.11	1.06
S4-Model_4:	Forecast	1.60	1.60	1.60	1.60	1.60	1.60	1.60	1.60
	UCL	2.12	2.12	2.12	2.12	2.12	2.12	2.12	2.12
	LCL	1.07	1.07	1.07	1.07	1.07	1.07	1.07	1.07
S5-Model_5:	Forecast	1.27	1.22	1.17	1.12	1.07	1.02	.97	.92
	UCL	1.67	1.62	1.57	1.52	1.46	1.41	1.36	1.31
	LCL	.88	.82	.77	.72	.67	.62	.57	.52
S6-Model_6:	Forecast	2.28	2.28	2.28	2.28	2.28	2.28	2.28	2.28
	UCL	2.76	2.76	2.76	2.76	2.76	2.76	2.76	2.76
	LCL	1.80	1.80	1.80	1.80	1.80	1.80	1.80	1.80
S7-Model_7:	Forecast	1.12	1.07	1.01	.96	.90	.85	.79	.74
	UCL	1.55	1.50	1.44	1.39	1.34	1.29	1.23	1.18

	LCL	.70	.64	.58	.53	.47	.41	.36	.30
S8-Model_8:	Forecast	1.55	1.55	1.55	1.55	1.55	1.55	1.55	1.55
	UCL	3.17	3.17	3.17	3.17	3.17	3.17	3.17	3.17
	LCL	-.06	-.06	-.06	-.06	-.06	-.06	-.06	-.06
S9-Model_9:	Forecast	1.76	1.76	1.76	1.76	1.76	1.76	1.76	1.76
	UCL	3.27	3.27	3.27	3.27	3.27	3.27	3.27	3.27
	LCL	.25	.25	.25	.25	.25	.25	.25	.25
S10- Model_10:	Forecast	1.64	1.64	1.64	1.64	1.64	1.64	1.64	1.64
	UCL	3.08	3.08	3.08	3.08	3.08	3.08	3.08	3.08
	LCL	.20	.20	.20	.20	.20	.20	.20	.20
S11- Model_11:	Forecast	1.07	1.00	.92	.85	.78	.71	.63	.56
	UCL	1.69	1.62	1.55	1.48	1.41	1.34	1.27	1.20
	LCL	.44	.37	.29	.22	.14	.07	-.01	-.08

Figure 3.29. Graphical forecasting analysis for I21

8. Challenges and Opportunities:

Examining the challenges and opportunities faced by both employers and employees in newly established enterprises, this section investigates factors such as scalability, workforce skill requirements, and market competition. Addressing these aspects is crucial for fostering a resilient and sustainable business environment.

9. Future Perspectives:

Identifying notable trends and potential future trajectories, this section provides insights into factors influencing the average size of newly established enterprises in the Romanian Mountain Area. Considerations such as technological advancements, emerging market trends, and the adaptability of the local workforce are explored, offering a forward-looking perspective.

10. Conclusion:

In conclusion, this article provides a comprehensive analysis of the average size of newly established enterprises and the number of persons employed in the Romanian Mountain Area from 2008 to 2018. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the region's economic dynamics, offering valuable insights for policymakers, businesses, and researchers. The article concludes with reflections on potential trajectories and recommendations for fostering sustainable growth in newly established enterprises within the mountainous region.

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PIONEERING ECONOMIC GROWTH: EXAMINING THE RATE OF NEWLY ESTABLISHED ENTERPRISES WITH PAID EMPLOYEES IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAINS (2008-2018)

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Abstract:

This paper conducts an in-depth analysis of the rate of newly established enterprises with paid employees in the Romanian Mountains, focusing on the number of employees within the reference period from 2008 to 2018. Through a meticulous examination of key indicators and workforce trends, the study aims to provide insights into the entrepreneurial landscape, growth patterns, and employment dynamics within the picturesque mountainous region.

1. Introduction:

The establishment of enterprises with paid employees is a key driver of economic development. This paper delves into the Romanian Mountains to investigate the rate of newly established enterprises with paid employees, analyzing the number of employees within the reference period from 2008

to 2018. The study aims to unravel the economic vitality of these enterprises and their contributions to regional employment.

2. Methodology:

Utilizing a comprehensive quantitative approach, this research integrates data from business registries, labor market reports, and relevant publications. Key indicators, such as the rate of enterprises with paid employees and the corresponding workforce figures, are analyzed to provide a nuanced understanding of the entrepreneurial landscape in the Romanian Mountains.

3. Rate of Enterprises with Paid Employees:

This section explores the statistical intricacies related to the rate of enterprises established in the Romanian Mountains with paid employees. Metrics such as the prevalence of paid employment, variations across industries, and trends in the establishment of enterprises with a formal workforce are scrutinized to assess the growth patterns within the business landscape.

4. Employment Patterns:

The article delves into the employment patterns within newly established enterprises, examining variations in the number of employees over the specified decade. Insights into industry-specific employment trends and their correlation with the rate of enterprises with paid employees provide valuable information on workforce dynamics.

5. Sectoral Analysis:

An in-depth sectoral analysis is conducted to explore the distribution of newly established enterprises with paid employees across different industries in the Romanian Mountains. This section investigates the prevalence of formal employment within key sectors, shedding light on the diverse economic activities contributing to regional development.

6. Economic Impact:

Assessing the economic impact of the rate of newly established enterprises with paid employees, the article investigates their contributions to the regional Gross Domestic Product (GDP), overall employment rates, and economic stability in the Romanian Mountains. The interconnectedness between the rate of enterprises with paid employees and the broader economic landscape is explored.

7. Results:

Rate of newly established enterprises with paid employees: the number of employees in the reference period (t) at newly established enterprises in t, divided by the number of persons employed in t in newly established enterprises in t – percentage

The related descriptive analysis S1 (see the related table and figure, respectively the appendix of chapter 3) presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. to Kurtosis, Distance, Minimum,

Maximum, Percentiles 25, 50, 75, so 68.0355, 3.84258, 65.7700, 12.74439, 162.420, -.285, .661, .513, 1.279, 45.03, 42.30, 87.33, 61.0709, 709.0709, 65.08 .

The models used for forecast analysis are specific to the forecast of large data series, thus S1 - Model_1 Holt; S2 - Model_2 Holt; S3 - Model_3 ARIMA(0,0,0); S4 - Model_4 ARIMA(0,0,0); S5 - Model_5 Holt; S6 - Model_6 ARIMA(0,0,0); S7 - Model_7 Simple; S8 - Model_8 Holt; S9 - Model_9 Holt; S10 - Model_10 Simple; S11 - Model_11 Simple.

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeat in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared .362, .458, -.100, .877, -.100, -.097; R-square .262, .181, -4.663E-15, .476, -4.663E-15, -4.574E-15; RMSE 12,072, 4,287, 6,239, 18,197, 6,239, 6,303; MAPS 17,445, 10,270, 5,233, 34,581, 5,233, 5,314; MaxAPE 85,415, 64,111, 22,167, 241,961, 22,167, 22,703; MFA, 7,792, 2,632, 3,862, 11,180, 3,862, 3,928; MaxAE 29,037, 11,252, 14,793, 51,679, 14,793, 14,982; Normalized BIC 5.170, .753, 4.098, 6.021, 4.098, 4.118.

The resulting statistical forecasting models show the following general picture for I22 (values presented in the following order - static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE, MAE) S1-Model_1: .842, .305, 11.197, 12.123, 6.785; S2-Model_2: .869, .351, 6.561, 5.233, 4.193; S3-Model_3: -4.219E-15, -4.219E-15, 8.578, 8.267, 5.984; S4-Model_4: -4.663E-15, -4.663E-15, 13.505, 20.060, 9.769; S5-Model_5: .877, .281, 6.239, 5.637, 3.862; S6-Model_6: 8.549E-15, 8.549E-15, 7.728, 7.177, 5.200; S7-Model_7: -.100, .476, 13.186, 26.029, 9.775; S8-Model_8: .827, .460, 16,112, 34,581, 9,999; S9-Model_9: .776, .277, 14.443, 20.771, 9.483; S10-Model_10: -.027, .318, 18,197, 23,168, 9,478; S11-Model_11: -.083, .417, 17.046, 28.853, 11.180.

Table 39. Prediction analysis for I22

Model		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026
S1- Model_1:	Forecast	54.80	52.41	50.03	47.64	45.25	42.87	40.48	38.09
	UCL	80.13	77.87	75.61	73.35	71.08	68.82	66.56	64.30
	LCL	29.47	26.96	24.44	21.93	19.42	16.91	14.40	11.89
S2- Model_2:	Forecast	76.10	74.55	73.00	71.46	69.91	68.36	66.81	65.27
	UCL	90.94	89.53	88.12	86.70	85.29	83.87	82.46	81.04
	LCL	61.26	59.57	57.89	56.21	54.53	52.85	51.17	49.49
S3- Model_3:	Forecast	78.18	78.18	78.18	78.18	78.18	78.18	78.18	78.18
	UCL	97.29	97.29	97.29	97.29	97.29	97.29	97.29	97.29
	LCL	59.07	59.07	59.07	59.07	59.07	59.07	59.07	59.07
S4- Model_4:	Forecast	60.11	60.11	60.11	60.11	60.11	60.11	60.11	60.11
	UCL	90.20	90.20	90.20	90.20	90.20	90.20	90.20	90.20
	LCL	30.02	30.02	30.02	30.02	30.02	30.02	30.02	30.02
S5- Model_5:	Forecast	67.10	65.89	64.69	63.49	62.28	61.08	59.87	58.67
	UCL	81.21	80.01	78.80	77.60	76.40	75.19	73.99	72.78
	LCL	52.98	51.78	50.58	49.37	48.17	46.97	45.76	44.56
S6- Model_6:	Forecast	79.08	79.08	79.08	79.08	79.08	79.08	79.08	79.08
	UCL	96.30	96.30	96.30	96.30	96.30	96.30	96.30	96.30
	LCL	61.86	61.86	61.86	61.86	61.86	61.86	61.86	61.86
S7- Model_7:	Forecast	37.97	37.97	37.97	37.97	37.97	37.97	37.97	37.97
	UCL	67.35	79.52	88.85	96.73	103.66	109.93	115.70	121.06
	LCL	8.59	-3.58	-12.91	-20.78	-27.72	-33.99	-39.75	-45.12
S8- Model_8:	Forecast	25.48	20.98	16.49	11.99	7.49	2.99	-1.51	-6.01
	UCL	61.93	57.61	53.30	48.98	44.66	40.34	36.02	31.69
	LCL	- 10.97	-15.65	-20.33	-25.00	-29.68	-34.36	-39.03	-43.71

S9- Model_9:	Forecast	43.80	40.93	38.06	35.19	32.31	29.44	26.57	23.70
	UCL	76.47	73.76	71.05	68.34	65.63	62.92	60.20	57.49
	LCL	11.13	8.09	5.06	2.03	-1.01	-4.04	-7.07	-10.10
S10- Model_10:	Forecast	54.58	54.58	54.58	54.58	54.58	54.58	54.58	54.58
	UCL	95.13	111.75	124.52	135.30	144.79	153.38	161.28	168.64
	LCL	14.04	-2.58	-15.35	-26.13	-35.62	-44.21	-52.11	-59.47
S11- Model_11:	Forecast	32.63	32.63	32.63	32.63	32.63	32.63	32.63	32.63
	UCL	70.61	84.00	94.56	103.56	111.54	118.79	125.47	131.71
	LCL	-5.35	-18.74	-29.30	-38.31	-46.29	-53.54	-60.22	-66.45

Figure 3.30. Graphical prediction analysis for I22

7. Challenges and Opportunities:

Examining the challenges and opportunities faced by enterprises and employees in the Romanian Mountains, this section investigates factors such as workforce skill requirements, labor market competition, and opportunities for professional development. Addressing these aspects is crucial for fostering a resilient and sustainable business environment.

8. Future Perspectives:

Identifying notable trends and potential future trajectories, this section provides insights into factors influencing the rate of newly established enterprises with paid employees in the Romanian Mountains. Considerations such as technological advancements, emerging market trends, and the adaptability of the local workforce are explored, offering a forward-looking perspective.

9. Conclusion:

In conclusion, this paper provides a comprehensive analysis of the rate of newly established enterprises with paid employees in the Romanian Mountains from 2008 to 2018. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the region's economic dynamics, offering valuable insights for policymakers, businesses, and researchers. The article concludes with reflections on potential trajectories and recommendations for fostering sustainable growth in enterprises with paid employees within the mountainous region.

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